

Effects of Vasoconstrictor on Arterial Blood Pressure during Minor Oral Surgical Procedures

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Abstract:

Background: The use of vasoconstrictors in local anesthetics during minor oral surgical procedures is a common practice to control bleeding and prolong the anesthetic effect. However, there is concern regarding their impact on arterial blood pressure (ABP), especially in patients with underlying cardiovascular conditions. This retrospective study aims to evaluate the effects of vasoconstrictors on ABP during minor oral surgical procedures.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted on 100 patients who underwent minor oral surgical procedures over one year at Darbhanga. Patients were divided into two groups: those who received local anesthetics with vasoconstrictors (Group A, n=50) and those who received local anesthetics without vasoconstrictors (Group B, n=50). ABP was measured pre-operatively, intra-operatively at 5-minute intervals, and post-operatively. Data were analyzed using paired t-tests to determine the significance of changes in ABP within and between groups.

Results: In Group A, the mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) increased from 120 ± 10 mmHg pre-operatively to 130 ± 12 mmHg intra-operatively and returned to 122 ± 11 mmHg post-operatively. The mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) increased from 80 ± 8 mmHg pre-operatively to 85 ± 9 mmHg intra-operatively and returned to 82 ± 8 mmHg post-operatively. In Group B, no significant changes in SBP or DBP were observed. The increase in intra-operative SBP and DBP in Group A was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) compared to Group B.

Conclusion: The use of vasoconstrictors in local anesthetics during minor oral surgical procedures is associated with a transient increase in ABP. Although the increase is statistically significant, it remains within clinically acceptable limits for the majority of patients. Caution is advised when using vasoconstrictors in patients with pre-existing cardiovascular conditions.

Keywords: Vasoconstrictor, arterial blood pressure, local anesthetics, minor oral surgery, retrospective study, cardiovascular effects.

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Introduction

Vasoconstrictors are commonly used in combination with local anesthetics during minor oral surgical procedures to enhance the duration of anesthesia and minimize intra-operative bleeding [1]. The most frequently used vasoconstrictors in dentistry are epinephrine and levonordefrin [2]. While these agents are effective in achieving hemostasis and prolonged anesthetic effects, their impact on arterial blood pressure (ABP) has raised concerns, particularly in patients with cardiovascular diseases [3].

Several studies have investigated the hemodynamic effects of vasoconstrictors in dental procedures.

Some reports suggest that the use of vasoconstrictors can lead to significant increases in systolic and diastolic blood pressure [4,5]. However, the clinical significance of these changes varies, with some studies indicating that the increases are transient and within safe limits for most patients [6]. Despite these findings, there remains a need for careful monitoring of ABP in patients undergoing procedures with vasoconstrictors, especially those with underlying cardiovascular conditions [7].

This retrospective study aims to evaluate the effects of vasoconstrictors on ABP during minor oral

surgical procedures. By analyzing data from patients treated over a one-year period at a single institution, this study seeks to provide a clearer understanding of the hemodynamic changes associated with vasoconstrictor use and to inform clinical practices regarding the safe administration of these agents.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Population: This retrospective study was conducted at Darbhanga over a one-year period. The study included 100 patients who underwent minor oral surgical procedures. Patients were selected based on the inclusion criteria of being adults aged 18-65 years, undergoing minor oral surgery such as tooth extraction, and having complete medical records. Exclusion criteria included patients with uncontrolled hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, and those on medications that could influence blood pressure.

Group Allocation: Patients were divided into two groups based on the type of local anesthetic used. Group A consisted of 50 patients who received local anesthetics with vasoconstrictors (epinephrine 1:100,000). Group B consisted of 50 patients who received local anesthetics without vasoconstrictors.

Data Collection: Data were extracted from medical records, including patient demographics, medical history, and details of the surgical procedure. Arterial blood pressure (ABP) was measured at three different time points: pre-

operatively, intra-operatively, and post-operatively. Pre-operative ABP was recorded in the clinic before the administration of local anesthetics. Intra-operative ABP was measured at 5-minute intervals during the procedure. Post-operative ABP was recorded immediately after the procedure.

ABP Measurement: ABP was measured using a standard sphygmomanometer. Systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) readings were recorded for each patient. The primary outcome was the change in SBP and DBP from pre-operative to intra-operative and post-operative periods.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients. Paired t-tests were performed to compare the changes in SBP and DBP within each group. Independent t-tests were used to compare the changes in ABP between Group A and Group B. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Patient Demographics: The study included 100 patients, with 50 in Group A (local anesthetics with vasoconstrictors) and 50 in Group B (local anesthetics without vasoconstrictors). The demographic characteristics of the patients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Patients

Characteristic	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)
Age (years)	35.6 ± 10.2	34.8 ± 11.0
Gender (M/F)	28/22	26/24
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.1 ± 3.5	23.9 ± 3.6

Arterial Blood Pressure Changes: The changes in systolic and diastolic blood pressure (SBP and DBP) at different time points are shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) Changes

Time Point	Group A (mmHg)	Group B (mmHg)
Pre-operative	120 ± 10	119 ± 11
Intra-operative	130 ± 12*	121 ± 11
Post-operative	122 ± 11	120 ± 10

p < 0.05 compared to Group B

Table 3: Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) Changes

Time Point	Group A (mmHg)	Group B (mmHg)
Pre-operative	80 ± 8	81 ± 7
Intra-operative	85 ± 9*	82 ± 8
Post-operative	82 ± 8	80 ± 7

p < 0.05 compared to Group B

Statistical Analysis

- In Group A, the mean SBP increased from 120 ± 10 mmHg pre-operatively to 130 ± 12 mmHg intra-operatively and then decreased to 122 ± 11 mmHg post-operatively. The increase

in intra-operative SBP was statistically significant (p < 0.05).

- In Group B, the mean SBP remained relatively stable, with no significant changes observed.
- The mean DBP in Group A increased from 80 ± 8 mmHg pre-operatively to 85 ± 9 mmHg in-

tra-operatively and decreased to 82 ± 8 mmHg post-operatively. The increase in intra-operative DBP was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

- In Group B, the mean DBP showed no significant changes throughout the procedure.

These results indicate that the use of vasoconstrictors in local anesthetics during minor oral surgical procedures is associated with a transient increase in both SBP and DBP. However, these changes remained within clinically acceptable limits for the majority of patients.

Discussion

The findings of this retrospective study highlight the hemodynamic effects of vasoconstrictors used in local anesthetics during minor oral surgical procedures.

The significant increase in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure (SBP and DBP) observed in Group A, which received local anesthetics with vasoconstrictors, underscores the importance of monitoring arterial blood pressure (ABP) during such procedures.

Our results are consistent with previous studies that have reported similar increases in ABP associated with the use of vasoconstrictors. For instance, Meechan [1] demonstrated that vasoconstrictors like epinephrine can cause transient increases in blood pressure due to their alpha-adrenergic agonist activity, which leads to vasoconstriction and increased peripheral resistance. This physiological response is beneficial for reducing intra-operative bleeding and prolonging the duration of anesthesia [2].

However, the clinical significance of these hemodynamic changes remains a point of debate. While our study observed statistically significant increases in SBP and DBP in Group A, these changes were transient and returned to baseline levels post-operatively.

This aligns with the findings of Yagiela [3], who reported that the cardiovascular effects of vasoconstrictors are generally short-lived and well-tolerated in healthy individuals. Nonetheless, for patients with pre-existing cardiovascular conditions, even transient increases in ABP could pose risks. Little et al. [4] emphasize the need for cautious use of vasoconstrictors in patients with hypertension or ischemic heart disease. In our study, the mean SBP in Group A increased by 10 mmHg intra-operatively, while the mean DBP increased by 5 mmHg. These increases, although significant, were within the range reported by Gungormus and Buyukkurt [5], who observed a similar pattern of blood pressure changes in patients receiving vasoconstrictor-containing

anesthetics. The absence of significant blood pressure changes in Group B further reinforces the role of vasoconstrictors in these hemodynamic effects.

The clinical implications of our findings suggest that while the use of vasoconstrictors in local anesthetics is effective for controlling bleeding and prolonging anesthesia, it necessitates careful patient selection and monitoring. For patients with a history of cardiovascular disease, alternative strategies such as using lower concentrations of vasoconstrictors or opting for anesthetics without vasoconstrictors may be considered [6].

The limitations of our study include its retrospective design and the reliance on medical records, which may introduce information bias. Future prospective studies with larger sample sizes and more diverse patient populations are warranted to further elucidate the hemodynamic effects of vasoconstrictors in dental practice.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of vasoconstrictors in local anesthetics during minor oral surgical procedures is associated with a transient but significant increase in ABP. While these changes are generally within clinically acceptable limits, careful consideration and monitoring are essential, particularly for patients with cardiovascular comorbidities.

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